

A cost-benefit analysis of pre-sorting by feller-buncher in underdeveloped short rotation poplar plantations

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Acknowledgments: This study was funded by the Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 745874 »Dendromass for Europe« (D4EU). Additional support was provided by the Pahernik foundation – University of Ljubljana. <https://www.uni-lj.si/news/news/6498/>"

Abstract

Underdeveloped tree crops (≤ 30 bone-dry tons ha^{-1}) offer a main harvest of biomass-trees, which lack the size and the form for producing a log. However, about 1/3 of the available stems may yield at least one log, which could significantly increase the overall value of the harvest. Under those circumstances, it may make sense sorting log-trees from biomass-trees at an early stage, rather than having a harvester or a processor to get through all trees just to chuck into the biomass piles almost 70 out of 100 trees. The Authors set up a controlled experiment to quantify the eventual benefit obtain by early pre-sorting, performed by the feller-buncher. Pre-sorting resulted in a 15% productivity loss for the feller-buncher, which was repaid by a 100% productivity increase for the processor. Considering the different hourly cost of the two machines, three Euros were saved for each additional Euro invested in pre-sorting. Pre-sorting made WTH a significantly cheaper option than CTL, whereas the two systems would be almost equally expensive when no pre-sorting was applied. Pre-sorting would also facilitate multiple-tree delimiting, implemented through the introduction of a chainflail; that is likely to further reduce harvesting cost, returning financial viability to the harvesting of underdeveloped plantations.

Keywords: Productivity; Cost; Log recovery; Multi-Tree; CTL; WTH

Introduction

Establishing and managing a tree farm is a costly venture that accrues reasonable profit only if value recovery is maximized. That is the rationale behind traditional poplar plantations, which base their profitability on a rich harvest of valuable veneer logs and are still quite successful worldwide (Heilman 1999). In contrast, most tree farm models designed to produce low-value biomass have failed, unless additional revenues could be accrued from other services, such as phytoremediation, recreation, environmental protection etc. (Helby et al. 2006). For that reason, most of the new plantations have been designed for the production of higher-value wood sorts than just industrial

50 biomass (Stanton et al. 2002, Werner et al. 2012). However, not all plantations are as successful as
51 their planners hoped: normally a certain proportion of the total acreage established by any one
52 company will grow less than expected and at the end of its rotation will not yield the quantity nor
53 the quality than one hoped for. That is even more frequent when the plantation model is new
54 and/or it is introduced to a new region, because of the uncertainty implied by the untested
55 association between species and sites. In those instances, a common solution is whole-tree
56 chipping, which allows minimizing cost (Spinelli et al. 2013). That generally achieves cost-cutting,
57 not profitability or even break-even. On the other hand, trying to recover the small amount of
58 higher-value assortments available amidst a score of biomass trees may incur a marginal cost higher
59 than the marginal revenue (Karttunen et al 2016, Pasanen et al. 2014). Picking out value trees from
60 a mass of low-quality individuals is time consuming, and it can be too expensive - especially if the
61 machine tasked with that job is a costly one (Kärhä 2011). For that reason, quality sorting should be
62 done with the least expensive piece equipment in the fleet, if at all. Furthermore, favourable
63 conditions should be sought, in which the equipment tasked with quality sorting may operate at
64 best. Past studies suggest that such could be the case of pre-sorting during felling (Lahrsen et al.
65 2021). That is the stage in the harvesting chain where the operator has the best view of the tree
66 being cut and can easily assess its potential. Furthermore, the tree must be cut anyway, so that the
67 eventual sorting task would simply amount to dumping cut trees into separate piles depending on
68 whether they can offer some valuable assortment or just raw biomass. Performed at any other stage
69 along the chain, sorting would require breaking the tree out of a bunch or stack, checking whether
70 it is good or not and eventually cutting off a log from those few trees that turn out having the right
71 form and size.

72
73 Therefore, pre-sorting during felling may seem a promising technique for value recovery in those
74 plantations that did not grow as hoped for and may offer too meagre a harvest for standard
75 collection, whether by the cut-to-length (CTL) or the whole-tree harvesting (WTH) system. The goal
76 of this study was to conduct a cost-benefit analysis of pre-sorting during felling, conducted in a
77 poplar plantation representative of the new tree farms being established in Central and Eastern
78 Europe (IPP 2019, Heilig et al. 2021). In particular, the study compared conventional cut-to-length
79 and whole-tree harvesting without pre-sorting against whole-tree harvesting with pre-sorting,
80 conducted by the same feller-buncher tasked with tree felling. The treatments on test were then:

- 81
82 1 – CTL: Conventional cut-to-length harvesting, without pre-sorting (single-tree)
83 2 – WTH: Conventional whole-tree harvesting, without pre-sorting (multi-tree)
84 3 – WTH Pre-sorting: Whole-tree harvesting with pre-sorting (multi-tree)

85
86 Pre-sorting was not tested in association with cut-to-length harvesting because that would require
87 introducing an additional machine to the CTL system and likely cancel any benefits eventually
88 accrued by pre-sorting. Pre-sorting was only attempted where it could be done by introducing a
89 small procedural change to an existing established routine, for fear that any stronger interventions
90 could irremediably compromise the already precarious balance. In all cases, the target assortment
91 was 4-m long logs with a minimum small end diameter (SED) of 7 cm. The ultimate goal was to
92 produce the largest proportion of logs at the lowest possible cost.

93
94 Therefore, the comparison was based on the following key performance indicators (KPI):

- 95
96 - harvesting cost
97 - log recovery rate.

98

99 The null hypothesis was that of no statistically significant differences between the three treatments
100 on test for each of the two KPIs.

101

102 **Materials and methods**

103 The three treatments were tested in January and February 2022 on one of the plantations
104 established in Western Slovakia by IKEA Industry for supplying their particle board factory in
105 Malacky. The test plantation was located in Pernek (48° 23' 55.04" N; 17° 04' 43.97" E in WGS84),
106 few kilometers northeast of the plant (48° 25' 01.81" N; 17° 02' 06.95"E). It was a 6-year-old poplar
107 stand established at a square spacing of 3.0 m x 2.0 m with hybrid poplar (*Populus x euramericana*
108 Dode (Guinier)), using the following mix of similar clones: AF13, AF 16 and AF18 (Landgraf et al.
109 2020, Meyer et al. 2021). The trees were planted on an ex-arable field, on flat and even terrain.
110 Weather during the test was consistently warm and dry, with occasional light rainfall. Air
111 temperature varied between -2 and +14 C°. All operations were conducted in daylight, normally
112 from 07:00 to 17:00.

113

114 CTL harvesting was applied using the classic combination of a harvester and a forwarder. A Rottne
115 H8D harvester (125 kW, 10 t own weight, head EGS 406 -
116 <https://www.rottnet.com/en/skogsmaskin/rottnet-h-8/>) was tasked with felling and processing the
117 trees, while a a Logset 5F GT 8-wheeled compact forwarder (140 kW, 15 t own weight, 12 t payload
118 capacity -<https://www.logset.com/en/forwarders/logset-5f-gt>) collected logs and tops and moved
119 them to separate piles at the roadside landing.

120

121 Under the WTH treatment, trees were felled and bunched using a 20-t Kobelco GS200 tracked
122 excavator equipped with a Silvaro 250K double-blade shear. Whole-tree bunches were taken to the
123 roadside landing using a Ponsse Buffalo heavy forwarder (140 kW, 15 t own weight, 12 t payload
124 capacity https://www.ponsse.com/products/forwarders/product/-/p/buffalo_8w#/). That machine
125 was large enough to load whole-tree bunches into its basket and carry them off the ground, to the
126 benefit of minimal soil contamination. Once there, trees were picked off the piles and processed
127 into 4 m lengths using a Nisula 425 C processor fitted to a Volvo EW 160 wheeled excavator. The
128 landing was obtained at the field's edge, along a service road, and was large enough for the
129 processor to operate comfortably. Logs and tops were piled in separate stacks along the road, for
130 later loading (logs) or chipping (tops) into trucks.

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132 The pre-sorting treatment was essentially the same as the WTH treatment, except that the feller-
133 buncher operator would pile log-trees and biomass-trees into separate piles, which would be
134 extracted separately with the Ponsse forwarder and unloaded into separate piles. Hence, the
135 processor would only work the pre-sorted tree piles and spend less time picking up and casting out
136 biomass-trees. Piles consisting of biomass-only trees would be chipped later, together with the piles
137 of tops, branches and undersize trees discarded by the processor.

138

139 Each machine was driven by its own operator, which was a qualified professional with significant
140 experience of his machine and specific task. All operators were co-opted into the study after
141 observing over a dozen of contractors and casting out those that were not considered
142 representative of the local pool of professional machine operators (Spinelli et al. 2022a).

143

144 Before engaging with data collection, all operators were tasked with working at least one full day in
145 the plantation outside the marked experimental blocks. That way, they could adjust to the study

146 routine and methods. The harvester and processor head measuring systems were checked and
147 calibrated on 10 trees before starting the experiment. Afterwards, calibration was checked on 2
148 trees at the beginning of each working day (Spinelli et al. 2022a).

149
150 The experimental design was a factorial scheme where each treatment was repeated 8 times (Figure
151 1). Each repetition consisted of one sample plot measuring approximately 15 x 50 m (700 m²). Plot
152 width was selected to represent the work frontage of the harvester and the feller-buncher, which
153 cut 5 row bands (5 x 3 m = 15 m). Plot length was chosen for including approximately 130 trees,
154 which previous studies of the same machine types found to be the amount of work normally
155 performed in about one scheduled machine hour (SMH). The experimental plots were alternately
156 assigned to the three treatments, on the assumption that a pure randomized design could confuse
157 the operators and increase the potential for attribution errors. In contrast, the alternate checker-
158 board design still allowed for an even spread of eventual site gradients but held less potential for
159 confusion (Spinelli et al. 2022a). The beginning and the end of each experimental plot was clearly
160 marked with bright paint to facilitate attribution. The circumference at breast height of all trees in
161 all plots was measured manually with a measuring tape and then converted into diameter at breast
162 height (DBH), over bark. Furthermore, 6 trees covering the whole DBH distribution were
163 destructively sampled to determine total height and weight, separately for the assumed log and
164 chip portions (Krejza et al. 2017; Urban et al. 2015). Destructive sampling allowed estimating an
165 allometric equation representing the relationship between DBH, total height and mass: that
166 equation was then used to predict the standing mass available on each individual sample plot
167 (Headlee and Zalesny 2019). Previous research has demonstrated that it is possible to build reliable
168 allometric models with such a small sample, when tree variability is as small as normally found in
169 even-aged clonal plantations (Hartmann 2010; Hjelm 2015; Verlinden et al. 2013). In any case, mass
170 estimates were later adjusted using ad-hoc correction factors that were obtained by matching the
171 pre-harvest inventory data with the actual harvest taken to the weighbridge available at the
172 receiving plant in Malacky. That was done separately for the log and for the chip portion obtained
173 from each of the three treatments, in order to account for variations in log recovery that might be
174 associated with any specific treatments (6 correction factors). Water mass fraction was determined
175 both at the time of destructive sampling during the pre-harvest inventory and at the time of scaling
176 on the factory weighbridge, so as to match dry mass pre-harvest estimates with dry mass post-
177 harvest weighbridge figures. In both cases, water mass fraction was determined with the gravimetric
178 method, according to EN ISO 18134-2:2015. Mean water mass fraction at delivery was 55%
179 (standard deviation = 2.7%).

180
181 Depending on site and treatment, the ratio between factory dry mass and inventory dry mass varied
182 from 0.63 to 0.86 with an overall average at 0.66 - meaning that the field inventory overestimated
183 actual harvest by about 50%.

184
185 At the time of harvesting, researchers determined for each sample plot the time taken to treat each
186 individual plot by each individual machine, using a stopwatch accurate to the second. Both
187 productive and delay times were recorded (Bjorheden et al. 1995), but delay time was eventually
188 excluded from the study and replaced by a 20% delay factor. That was done because the time spent
189 on each sample plot was not long enough to accurately estimate the long-term incidence of delay
190 time. The 20% increase applied to the data was consistent with the findings of previous published
191 studies, with special reference to the harvesting of plantation forests (Spinelli and Visser 2008). That
192 figure was also quite close to the sum of all delays recorded during the complete study, as conducted
193 on the 24 experimental plots.

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Since the capacity of both forwarders would often exceed the mass of wood on one experimental plot, a payload fill rate was estimated for each trip and applied as a reduction factor to travel time, on the assumption that a forwarder would normally travel with a full load. The inherently subjective character of that estimate was minimized by taking pictures of each load and submitting them to a panel of five experts, together with a reference picture of the forwarder with a full load. The experts were then asked to give their own best estimate of the payload fill rate for each load, and the value eventually adopted into the study was the one receiving most preferences, or the central one if each expert returned a different figure.

All wood harvested from the experimental plots was taken to the same landing, and therefore the extraction distance was the same for all treatments on test. In any case, distance was estimated from Google Earth pictures, from the center of the sample plot to the center of the roadside landing and it was 370 m as average. Distance between the strip roads was 15 m. Mean load concentration was 3.3 BDT (or 7.3 green t) per 100 m.

The plot-level time study was accompanied by a parallel cycle-level elemental time study (Magagnotti et al. 2011) that covered about half of the harvester, feller-buncher and processor cycles on each sample plot, plus all the forwarder cycles (Annex A). The goal of the elemental time study was to determine if treatment would specifically impact one or more work steps within the complete task; in particular, it aimed at determining whether and how pre-sorting would affect the work pattern of the feller-buncher and the processor, which were the units directly impacted by it. Similarly, the cycle-level time study was used to determine if pre-sorting would produce different tree rejection rates (i.e. larger or smaller proportions of no-log trees) and thus explain possible differences in log yield.

Machine cost was assumed to be the rates actually charged by the service providers. These were: 69 € per scheduled machine hour (SMH) for the harvester, 53 € SMH⁻¹ for the compact forwarder, 45 € SMH⁻¹ for the feller-buncher, 75 € SMH⁻¹ for the heavy forwarder and 47 € SMH⁻¹ for the processor. The Authors acknowledge that the commercial rates charged by individual operators can hardly offer a general reference and they encourage readers operating under substantially different economic conditions to recalculate harvesting cost using their own rates and the productivity data presented in this paper. Otherwise, one could use official rates, but those were not available for the region where this study was conducted. In any case, the rates charged by the operators contracted for this study were in line with those charged by other service providers in the region, and therefore the selected rates can be taken as generally representative of the area (Spinelli et al. 2022a). However, those rates were much lower than charged by neighboring Austrian contractors, located just across the border – which stresses the importance of recalculating cost whenever market conditions differ significantly from those described in this paper (Spinelli et al. 2022b).

Data analysis aimed at estimating meaningful measures of centrality for each of the three treatments on test, and at determining if the differences found between them were statistically significant. The dataset comprised of 8 repetitions per treatment, each repetition represented by one sample plot. Given such relatively small number of data and the frequent violation of the normality assumptions, the analysis was conducted with non-parametric techniques, which are robust against such violations and still reasonably accurate. In particular, the Kruskal-Wallis multiple comparison test was used for a general comparison between treatments, while the Mann-Whitney unpaired comparison test was used for comparing the unsorted against the pre-sorted

242 WTH treatment, and the best between the two WTH treatments against the CTL treatment. For all
243 analyses, the significance level was set at $\alpha < 0.05$. The analyses were implemented with the software
244 SAS Statview. In order to facilitate comparison between the WTH and CTL treatments, the separate
245 time consumption and cost figures obtained for the feller-buncher and the processor under the
246 WTH treatment were consolidated into one single felling and processing time consumption and cost
247 figure per sample plot, which was functionally equivalent to the felling and processing work
248 sequence conducted within a single pass by the harvester, under the CTL treatment. That way, one
249 would have one figure for felling and processing and one figure for forwarding for each of the sample
250 plots, regardless of treatment.

251

252 **Results**

253 Median diameter at breast height (DBH) was 10 cm and median height 8 m, without any significant
254 differences between treatments. No significant differences were found for tree mass and stand
255 stocking either, with medians at 14 kg dry matter (DM) and 22 bone dry tons (BDT) per hectare,
256 respectively (Table 1). Log yield was low, with medians between 17% and 25% of the total standing
257 mass; it was higher for the CTL treatment, but that difference was not statistically significant and
258 the information can be considered as suggestive rather than conclusive.

259

260 Cumulated felling and processing productivity was significantly higher for the CTL harvester, while
261 cost was significantly lower for the WTH pre-sort treatment. The latter accrued a 20% cost saving,
262 compared with both alternatives. (Table 2). Forwarding was significantly more productive under the
263 WTH treatment, since a larger and more powerful machine was deployed. However, that machine
264 was also more expensive and the productivity margin (12%) was smaller than the additional cost
265 per hour (40%), resulting into a significantly higher forwarding cost for both WTH treatments. That
266 eroded the benefits accrued at felling and processing and resulted in a tied match when it came to
267 the overall harvesting cost (i.e. felling, processing and forwarding: from standing trees to logs and
268 biomass at the roadside landing). In fact, the data suggested a harvesting cost stratification whereby
269 WTH > CTL > WTH Pre-sort, but those differences were not significant at 5% level.

270

271 In fact, forwarding was somewhat inefficient under all treatments, given the difficulty of assembling
272 large enough loads with the lightweight bulky materials available on site. Mean full payload was 2.8
273 BDT, 2.2 BDT and 4.0 BDT respectively for the Logset forwarder (CTL) loaded with logs and with tops,
274 and for the Ponsse forwarder (WTH). Expressed as fresh weight, those figures would amount to 6.2,
275 4.8 and 8.8 green tons, respectively. That is: 55%, 40% and 60% of the maximum rated payload of
276 the respective forwarder. Even with 4-m logs under the CTL treatment, the compact forwarder was
277 unable to pack more than 60% of its rated payload – and logs represented only 25% of the total
278 mass on site, the rest being much bulkier tops and branches!

279

280 The specific benefits of pre-sorting are best appreciated through a direct comparison between the
281 two WTH treatments, conducted exactly under the same conditions: site, machines and operators
282 (Table 3). Essentially, pre-sorting resulted in a 15% productivity loss for the feller-buncher, which
283 was repaid by a 100% productivity increase for the processor. The additional felling cost was 2.7 €
284 BDT⁻¹, but that allowed saving 8.8 € BDT⁻¹ in processing cost; three Euros were saved for each
285 additional Euro invested in pre-sorting, which seemed a pretty good deal. Those differences were
286 statistically significant, whereas the difference in forwarding cost was not. However, that difference
287 went the opposite direction than that found for felling and processing, which increased the
288 variability of the overall cost figures to the point where the statistical analysis turned inconclusive.
289 Therefore, the 15% saving on overall harvesting cost accrued through pre-sorting could only be

290 taken as suggestive ($p=0.14$). However, when the data were corrected by replacing the actual
291 forwarding cost with its overall average across treatments, then the analysis confirmed the
292 statistical significance ($p=0.03$) of that same cost saving figure (15%).

293

294 The detailed cycle level time study was unable to detect a significant productivity difference for the
295 feller buncher under any of the two treatments (Table 4). Under the unsorted treatment, larger
296 accumulations (3 trees per cycle instead of 2) were significantly more frequent than under the pre-
297 sorted treatment. However, that incurred a proportionally larger time consumption, so the
298 productivity was approximately the same. Taken together, the results of the sample plot-level and
299 the cycle-level studies indicated that any productivity losses caused by the pre-sorting task were
300 small or altogether negligible.

301

302 The detailed cycle level time study showed that processor productivity in trees per hour was slightly
303 higher (13%) under the unsorted treatment, compared with pre-sorted one, and that the difference
304 was statistically significant (Table 5). That was the logical consequence of more trees being picked
305 up, checked and casted away into the biomass pile without processing, which resulted in the
306 average time consumption per tree being shorter under than unsorted treatment. What really
307 made the difference was that after pre-sorting 60% of the trees in the processor piles were log-
308 worthy, while that number dropped to 30% if no pre-sorting was performed. In short, the original
309 crop consisted of 70% biomass-trees, all of which had to be picked up by the processor just to be
310 chucked into the biomass pile, thus leading to an accumulation of void cycles that would not
311 produce any logs and represented wasted processor time. Pre-sorting resulted in the processor
312 having to handle 20 biomass-trees for every 30 log-trees, that is: 50 cycles (30 log-trees + 20
313 biomass-trees) instead of 100 (30 log-trees + 70 biomass-trees) under the unsorted treatment. It
314 was such dramatic reduction in the number of processor cycles required to treat a given lot that
315 accrued the large savings shown in Table 3.

316

317 The direct match between CTL and WTH harvesting (pre-sorting) indicated the latter as the likely
318 winner, with an 8.5% cost saving (i.e. 4 € BDT⁻¹ - Table 6). That difference was borderline significant
319 ($p = 0.06$), but given the relatively small number of observations it could be taken as strongly
320 indicative of a real stratification of the data, which could also be observed in the box plot (Figure 2).

321

322 Essentially, switching from CTL to WTH harvesting (pre-sorted) accrued a 7.5 € BDT⁻¹ saving in felling
323 and processing cost and incurred a 3.6 € BDT⁻¹ loss in forwarding cost. Savings were twice as large
324 as costs, which should logically result in an overall reduction of the harvesting bill: that was one
325 more reason why one should consider with much attention the borderline significant difference
326 reported for total cost in the last row of table 6.

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329 Discussion

330 Before getting too deep into the results it is fair to acknowledge the main limitations of this study,
331 so that readers can decide to what extent they want to trust our conclusions as a guide for future
332 practical use. We believe that a main limitation of this study is the small number of replications,
333 which may have been too few for emerging the finer differences between treatments. However,
334 while the observations were relatively few, each of them contained enough work for achieving
335 stable performance levels. Therefore, the experiment was able to disclose significant differences
336 and offer good insights into the selected systems. Furthermore, the raw data were not manipulated
337 in any way, in order to keep their genuine value and avoid introducing any bias. For that reason,

338 non-parametric statistics were preferred to transformations. The idea was that readers should be
339 able to follow and understand the whole process throughout, without complicated analyses or
340 mysterious black boxes.

341
342 A further limitation of the study was the inevitable impact of operator effect (Purfürst and Erler
343 2011, Leonello et al. 2012). Ideally, that should have been included into the experiment by recruiting
344 multiple operators (Spinelli and Moura 2019), but such intervention would have dramatically
345 expanded the cost and the complexity of the experiment. For that very reason, the inclusion of
346 multiple operators is a very rare occurrence in forest operations studies - whether controlled or
347 observational. In that regard, recommended best practice consists of selecting competent
348 professionals that are representative of the larger pool of available operators, after observing them
349 at work (Košir et al 2015). That was done here; even if there is no guarantee that the results of the
350 system comparison (CTL vs. WTH) could have not been confounded to some extent by minor
351 variations in operator competence, we believe that operator effect was unlikely to be as strong as
352 to overpower important performance differences. Furthermore, operator effect may have
353 confounded the comparison between CTL and WTH, but not that between unsorted and sorted
354 treatment, given that the very same operators were deployed for both treatments.

355
356 Support to cautious generalization is obtained from the existing literature. Few references can be
357 found that specifically address the effect of pre-sorting on feller-buncher performance, but all those
358 few agree with the direction and the size of effects reported here; they indicate that pre-sorting
359 leads to a small but significant reduction of feller-buncher productivity, estimated between 5%
360 (Mikkonen 1976, Gingras 1996) and 10% (Gingras and Godin 2001, Kizha and Han 2016). In fact,
361 differences may even be non-significant when only two sorts are separated (McMorland 2008). The
362 literature also indicates that pre-sorting by feller-buncher significantly increases the productivity of
363 a processor (Meek 1995), which would incur larger losses than the feller buncher, if forced to sort
364 its feedstock (i.e. 15-30% losses according to Gingras 1996).

365
366 In fact, the crux of the matter is the small proportion of log-trees offered by underdeveloped
367 plantations. Separating felling from processing and delegating the two tasks to separate machines
368 is generally done in the hope that dedicating a specialized and cheaper machine to each individual
369 task will result in a higher productivity and lower cost, so that the sum of the two separate costs will
370 be lower than the cost incurred when deploying an integrated single-pass cut-to-length harvester
371 for the same task. That is always a tough match between the principle of specialization and that of
372 redundancy – since the two separate machines will result in the same work object being picked up
373 and laid down twice, which is not inherently efficient. In our case, however, task separation resulted
374 in redundancy only for a small proportion of the trees, since pre-sorting allowed setting aside those
375 trees that did not need a second pass by the processor. So, task separation did not cause
376 redundancy, but rather avoided it – because it prevented the redundant delimiting and measuring
377 performed by the CTL harvester, which would end with rejection 70% of the times.

378
379 In that regard, we cannot fail to notice that even after pre-sorting, 40% of the trees fed to the
380 processor were going to be cast away, all the same. While that was a large improvement over the
381 unsorted treatment, one still wonders if the feller-buncher operator could make a better selection
382 without sacrificing too many log trees. Further research could address the use of sensors for
383 assisting with tree size estimate and enable a more accurate selection: that way one could reduce
384 the proportion of biomass-trees ending into the log-tree pile, without increasing the wastage of
385 valuable log-trees (Forsman et al. 2016).

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In fact, log recovery must also depend on harvester or processor head characteristics, as well as on the individual skill of the operators. We have already explained why we believe that the operators selected had similar good skills and were representative of the larger operator population available in the region; however, the two machines were definitely different. The dedicated harvester was more technologically advanced (and expensive) than the excavator-based processor. Visual observation during the extended time study suggested that the processor head design and setting were less tolerant of malformed trees, which struggled to pass through the knives and would often break. Therefore, one may wonder if significant improvements in log yield and productivity could be obtained by replacing the currently used processor head with another model, possibly more suited to the task (Spinelli et al. 2002, Magagnotti et al. 2021). In that regard, a more radical solution would consist in replacing the processor with a multi-tree delimber, such as a chainflail. The latter would work best with pre-sorted small trees, likely offering higher productivity and log yield than the single-tree equipment used in this test. Use of a chainflail may allow bumping many borderline trees into the log-tree pile, since that machine is more tolerant of stem malformation than most cut-to-length heads (Spinelli et al 2022c). In that regard, it is worth mentioning that the market offers multi-tree CTL harvesters and processors that could be used profitably for mass-processing pre-sorted trees or conduct pre-sorting and mass-processing at the felling stage. They were not included in the test because those machines are still relatively few (none was available in the area) and because previous tests on short-rotation poplar indicated that the production benefit they can accrue is relatively small (Magagnotti et al. 2021). Finally, one may also try cut the cost of CTL harvesting by replacing the thinning processor with a light excavator-based or tractor-based harvester. However, such equipment is often less productive than its dedicated counterpart and it is generally resorted to when market conditions prevent full utilization of a specialized machine so that investment cost must be minimized (Bergroth et al. 2022).

Further improvements may target forwarding. The study highlighted three important issues when it came to forwarding: first, the very low payload utilization achieved for all treatments on test; second, the better performance achieved by the lighter of the two machines; third the possibly better performance achieved by the heavier machine under the unsorted treatment, compared with the pre-sorting treatment. First things first: low payload utilization is a common challenge when forwarding residues and whole trees, due to their bulky nature; however, here that happened with log loads, too. IKEA grows poplar for manufacturing an innovative lightweight board – so, low density is the essential characteristic of the wood obtained from those plantations: there is no way around it. Forwarders used in short rotation poplar do not need to be particularly powerful or robust: they will inevitably carry relatively light loads and will travel on easy terrain, with no important obstacles or inclines that may tax the smallest engine. If one could expand the load space of a thinning forwarder, that would be more than enough, and it may even be worthwhile designing a dedicated SRP model - lighter and cheaper than most standard units. The potential benefit of such an approach is confirmed by the second issue in the list: the heavy forwarder incurred a higher extraction cost than the smaller compact forwarder, because the advantage offered by its larger size and power could not be brought to bear and the higher hourly rate was not offset by a proportionally higher productivity. Finally, one should consider the better performance obtained by the same heavy forwarder under the unsorted WTH treatment, compared with the pre-sorted WTH treatment. There, data were not conclusive, but only suggestive. Yet, they pointed at something that has already been experienced in other studies: the inverse relationship between forwarder productivity and biomass stocking (Manner et al. 2013, Väätäinen et al. 2006). As applied in this experiment, pre-sorting effectively resulted in a reduction of biomass stocking, since the forwarder

434 had to make two passes for the separate collection of the two tree sorts. There, redundancy could
435 be avoided by introducing a partitioned load bay, offered as optional by several manufacturers. Such
436 modification would allow packing multiple sorts into the same load in a single pass and speed up
437 extraction. Essentially, SRP requires a small forwarder with a very large bunk, fitted with a mobile
438 partition; such machine would allow rebalancing cost with performance, thus maximizing cost-
439 efficiency. Since whole trees must be handled, the loader should be quite powerful and it could also
440 be fitted with a heel, to improve control of long loads (US Forest service 2022). Introducing a heel
441 would incur a small additional cost but could improve handling efficiency and reduce breakage risk,
442 especially when dealing with the brittle stems offered by some low-density clones (Zhang et al.
443 2003).

444

445 **Conclusions**

446 Pre-sorting of log-trees offers significant efficiency benefits when harvesting underdeveloped short
447 rotation poplar. First and foremost, it avoids burdening the cut-to-length processor with fruitless
448 work that does not result in the production of any logs. Furthermore, it facilitates the introduction
449 of multi-tree delimiting technologies, which could result in a marked increase of productivity and
450 log yield. In that case, WTH would likely outperform CTL harvesting and help take harvesting cost
451 back within the profitability limits set by the operation managers. Of course, one should always
452 balance the additional cost of integrated harvesting (logs + chips) against the savings accrued
453 through whole-tree chipping, after accounting for the amount of log material actually recovered
454 and the price difference between logs and whole-tree chips.

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457 **Acknowledgments**

458 This study was funded by the Bio Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's
459 Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 745874 »Dendromass
460 for Europe« (D4EU). Additional support was provided by the Pahernik foundation – University of
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619 **Annex A – Description of the time elements for the cycle-level study**

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621 A1. Harvester

622 Move = Wheels are turning while no other tasks are being performed

623 Fell = From the moment the boom extend towards a tree to the moment when the stem starts being fed
624 through the head

625 Process = From the moment the stem starts being fed through the head to the moment the last log is cut

626 Drop top = From the moment the last log is cut to the moment the top is released onto the ground or pile

627 Stack = Logs and tops are moved and/or rearranged

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629 A2. Processor

630 As for the harvester, except that Fell is replaced by Grab = From the moment the boom extend towards the
631 tree pile to the moment when the stem starts being fed through the head

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633 A3. Feller-Buncher

634 Move = Tracks are turning while no other tasks are being performed

635 Fell = From the moment the boom extend towards a tree to the moment when the tree or tree bunch is moved
636 towards the dumping site

637 Handle = From the moment the tree or tree bunch is moved towards the dumping site to the moment the
638 head is empty and is positioned towards the work frontage.

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640 A4. Forwarder

641 Travel empty = The forwarder leaves the landing and moves to its first loading station

642 Loading = From the moment the forwarder reaches its first loading station to the moment when it has
643 completed its load and moves towards the landing

644 Travel loaded = The forwarder leaves the loading site and reaches the roadside landing, stopping by the
645 designated stack

646 Unloading = From the moment the forwarder stops by the designated stack to when it leaves the landing

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Table 1. Characteristics of the experimental sample plots (median values)

Treatment		CTL	WTH	WTH Pre-Sort	
Obs	n°	8	8	8	P-Value
Trees	n°	125	128	125	0.6049
DBH	Cm	10.0	9.8	10.0	0.7464
Height	M	8.1	8.1	8.1	0.7464
Tree mass	kg DM	13.7	14.5	13.8	0.4415
Mass	BDT	1.7	1.9	1.7	0.4415
Stocking	BDT ha ⁻¹	22.1	22.6	22.6	0.6360
Log Yield	%	24.7	16.7	20.3	0.3526

Notes: CTL = Cut-to-Length; WTH = Whole-Tree Harvesting; DBH = Diameter at breast height; DM = Dry Matter; BDT = Bone-Dry ton (0% water mass fraction); Log Yield % = 100 * Log Mass/Total Mass; KW = Kruskal-Wallis test (used to estimate the reported p-Values)

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Table 2. Harvesting productivity and cost (median values)

Treatment		CTL	WTH	WTH Pre-Sort	p-Value
Obs	n°	8	8	8	
Felling	BDT SMH ⁻¹	2.0	1.4	1.7	0.0007
Processing	€ BDT ⁻¹	33.9	33.9	26.5	0.0096
Forwarding	BDT SMH ⁻¹	4.6	5.1	4.9	0.0388
	€ BDT ⁻¹	11.6	14.6	15.3	0.0094
Total	€ BDT ⁻¹	46.1	49.5	42.2	0.1451

Notes: CTL = Cut-to-Length; WTH = Whole-Tree Harvesting; BDT = Bone-Dry ton (0% water mass fraction); SMH = Scheduled Machine Hour, including delays (20%); different superscript letters on mean values on the same row indicate a statistically significant difference at the 5% level. KW = Kruskal-Wallis test (used to estimate the reported p-Values)

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Table 3. Harvesting productivity and cost (median values): WTH unsorted vs. WTH pre-sorting

		Unsorted	Pre- sorting	Delta	Delta %	P-Value MW
Felling	BDT SMH ⁻¹	2.9	2.4	-0.4	-14.9	0.0117
	€ BDT ⁻¹	15.6	18.3	2.7	17.1	0.0117
Processing	BDT SMH ⁻¹	2.7	5.5	2.8	103.7	0.0033
	€ BDT ⁻¹	17.3	8.5	-8.8	-51.0	0.0033
Forwarding	BDT SMH ⁻¹	5.1	4.9	-0.2	-4.5	0.2936
	€ BDT ⁻¹	14.6	15.3	0.6	4.4	0.2936
Total	€ BDT ⁻¹	49.5	42.2	-7.3	-14.8	0.1415
Forwarding corrected and equalized						
Total	€ BDT ⁻¹	48.5	41.1	-7.4	-15.3	0.0274

Notes: WTH = Whole-Tree Harvesting; BDT = Bone-Dry ton (0% water mass fraction); SMH = Scheduled Machine Hour, including delays (20%); MW = Mann-Whitney test (used to estimate the reported p-Values); Obs. = 8 replications per treatment – sample plot-level study; “Forwarding corrected and equalized” means that the same mean forwarding cost was adopted for WTH regardless of pre-sorting, since there was a difference in forwarding cost between WTH unsorted and pre-sorted, but that was not statistically significant.

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Table 4. Feller-buncher productivity (median values from the cycle-level study)

		Unsorted	Pre- sorting	P-Value MW
Obs	n°	285	283	
Cycle time	s	36	30	<0.0001
Trees cycle ⁻¹	n°	2.7	2.3	<0.0001
Cycles PMH ⁻¹	n°	100	120	<0.0001
Trees PMH ⁻¹	n°	270	276	0.0594

Notes: PMH = Productive Machine Hour, excluding all delays (20%); MW = Mann-Whitney test (used to estimate the reported p-Values).

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Table 5. Processor productivity (median values from the cycle-level study)

		Unsorted	Pre- sorting	P-Value MW
Obs	n°	497	385	
Logs	n° tree ⁻¹	0.3	0.6	<0.0001
Cycle time	s	15	17	0.0002
Trees cycle ⁻¹	n°	1	1	>0.9999
Cycles PMH ⁻¹	n°	240	212	0.0002
Trees PMH ⁻¹	n°	240	212	0.0002
Log trees	%	30	60	0.0008

Notes: PMH = Productive Machine Hour, excluding all delays (20%); MW = Mann-Whitney test (used to estimate the reported p-Values).

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Table 6. Harvesting productivity and cost (median values): CTL vs. WTH pre-sorting

		CTL	WTH	Delta	Delta %	P-Value
		Pre-sorting				MW
Felling &	BDT SMH ⁻¹	2.0	1.7	-0.3	-15.3	0.0063
Processing	€ BDT ⁻¹	34.0	26.5	-7.5	-22.0	0.0033
Forwarding	BDT SMH ⁻¹	4.6	4.9	0.3	7.7	0.0357
	€ BDT ⁻¹	11.6	15.3	3.6	31.3	0.0033
Total	€ BDT ⁻¹	46.1	42.2	-3.9	-8.5	0.0587

Notes: CTL = Cut-to-Length; WTH = Whole-Tree Harvesting; BDT = Bone-Dry ton (0% water mass fraction); SMH = Scheduled Machine Hour, including delays (20%); MW = Mann-Whitney test (used to estimate the reported p-Values; Obs. = 8 replications per treatment – sample plot-level study.

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730 **Figure 1.** Experimental design – distribution of treatments among sample plots

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Figure 2. Box plot of total harvesting cost (standing tree to assortments at roadside)

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